

Bridging predictions with experimental reality: *In vitro* evaluation of phenolic natural products as SARS-CoV-2 exoribonuclease inhibitors

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ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 exoribonuclease (ExoN) is essential for viral replication, contributing to proofreading, RNA synthesis, and genomic RNA recombination. As such, it represents a promising target for antiviral drugs. Several low-molecular-weight inhibitors, including disulfiram and aurintricarboxylic acid (ATA), have been reported to inhibit ExoN activity. Computational studies have also suggested that various natural phenolic compounds may inhibit ExoN; however, their inhibitory potency remains largely unknown. In this study, we systematically evaluated the inhibitory potency of 60 phenolic phytochemicals, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, coumarins, and other related compounds, using a dual-assay approach, with ATA as the reference inhibitor. Initially, we used nano-differential scanning fluorimetry to assess the thermal stabilization or destabilization of the enzyme induced by compound binding. Subsequently, we performed a TBE-PAGE-based enzymatic activity assay to examine ExoN activity inhibition. Selected compounds were then validated using a FRET-based enzymatic assay. While none of the compounds achieved the ATA's inhibitory efficacy, three compounds demonstrated measurable inhibitory activity: myricetin ($IC_{50} = 142 \mu M$), ellagic acid ($IC_{50} = 44.4 \mu M$), and shikonin ($IC_{50} = 7.92 \mu M$). Our dual assay approach, complemented by crosslinking experiments, revealed that shikonin exhibits a distinct inhibitory mechanism, possibly involving the disruption of ExoN subunit interactions. These findings emphasize the necessity of experimental validation following *in silico* screening, particularly for promiscuous chemicals such as phenolic natural products. This approach may help to narrow down rationally designed compounds for further optimization.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, coronaviruses (CoVs) have become a major threat to human health, causing outbreaks of severe respiratory diseases. The emergence of SARS-CoV-2, the causative agent of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), led to a global pandemic that had a significant impact on public health and socio-economic structures worldwide. Although the acute phase of the pandemic has passed, SARS-CoV-2 continues to pose a threat, particularly to vulnerable populations [48]. While vaccines and multiple small-molecule therapeutics have been approved for use against the disease, challenges persist due to the possibility of drug resistance and viral adaptation. Consequently, the development of novel, effective antiviral strategies to combat CoVs remains an important ongoing effort [21].

One approach to designing new antivirals is to interfere with

essential steps in the viral replication cycle [21]. RNA synthesis typically represents a vital target for novel drugs in RNA viruses such as CoVs. In CoVs, this process is orchestrated by the replication-transcription complex (RTC), a multi-protein machinery composed of nine non-structural proteins (nsps). The RTC facilitates the synthesis of subgenomic RNAs and replication of the approximately 30 kb coronaviral genome [47]. A key and unique feature of RNA synthesis in CoVs is the use of 3'-5' exoribonuclease (ExoN) as an independent proofreading factor. ExoN is an Mg^{2+} -dependent enzyme, located within the N-terminal domain of the bifunctional nsp14; the C-terminal domain of nsp14 is participates in RNA capping [43]. The ExoN catalytic activity is further significantly increased by interaction with the nsp10 cofactor, which stabilizes the ExoN active site [4]. This proofreading mechanism is crucial in maintaining the fidelity of the RTC, as shown in studies documenting that CoVs lacking the ExoN activity exhibit reduced viability [32].

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Proofreading is a major challenge for antiviral therapies, as it can cause resistance to nucleoside analogues, a key type of antiviral drugs [42]. By excising the incorporated nucleotide analogues, ExoN can counteract the effects of these inhibitors, potentially reducing their efficacy. Beyond its proofreading role, it has also been proposed that ExoN contributes to genomic recombination and the suppression of the immune response, further highlighting its importance in CoV biology [43].

Due to its role in viral replication, ExoN has consistently been explored as a target for small-molecule inhibitors. Notably, using ExoN inhibitors to improve the effectiveness of nucleotide analogues such as Remdesivir or Molnupiravir has been proposed as a promising strategy [19]. Several small molecules capable of ExoN inhibition have been identified. These include Zn²⁺ ejectors such as disulfiram and ebselen [7] and structural analogues of the catechol derivative dynasore [2]. Moreover, high-throughput screening approaches focusing on large libraries of compounds have also been employed successfully, resulting in the discovery of aurintricarboxylic acid (ATA) and patulin [5] as well as dual ExoN/methyltransferase inhibitors [13]. Despite these efforts, no clinically suitable compound has yet been identified.

Large-scale computational methods are an integral part of modern drug discovery. These approaches not only enable structure-based drug design but also facilitate virtual screenings during the initial testing phase of drug repurposing efforts [23,33]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, numerous *in silico* studies were conducted to identify novel inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 proteins [30,34,46]. In the case of ExoN, various phenolic natural products have emerged as promising inhibitory candidates. Molecules such as coumarins, phenolic terpenoids, and flavonoids, as well as their glycosides, have been identified as potential binders in multiple computational studies ([18,19,10][25,31,45]). Furthermore, phenolic compounds can act as specific chelators. The inhibition of metalloenzymes through specific chelation is a well-known phenomenon [16] and has been proposed as a potential strategy against SARS-CoV-2 ExoN [14]. Phenolic compounds also offer additional antioxidant, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory benefits [41]. Although Chaves et al. Chaves et al., [6] conducted a comprehensive analysis of seven flavonoids and discovered that none of them specifically target ExoN, there are still many promising phenolic phytochemicals that require experimental investigation.

In this study, we systematically evaluated 60 compounds (Tab. S1) for their ability to inhibit SARS-CoV-2 ExoN. The panel primarily comprised phenolic natural products identified in previous *in silico* studies or recognized for their favorable drug-like properties and metal-chelating potential. These included caffeic acid, ferulic acid, and related precursors [12], as well as smaller precursor molecules. By combining thermal stability and enzyme activity assays, we provide a comprehensive comparison of their inhibitory potency. Notably, our experimental results correlated only weakly with *in silico* predictions, highlighting the limitations of computational screening. Nevertheless, we identified shikonin as a moderate ExoN inhibitor and found preliminary evidence suggesting a distinct mechanism.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Expression vectors

The vector encoding both individual *nsp14* and *nsp10* genes was obtained from Addgene (Addgene plasmid #159613). The *nsp10* coding sequence was subcloned into a pET41 vector containing a sequence encoding a GST tag followed by a TEV protease cleavage site. For *nsp14* expression, the gene was inserted into a modified pNEA vector that included an N-terminal tagging by His-MBP separated by a 3 C protease cleavage site.

2.2. Protein expression, isolation and purification

2.2.1. *nsp14*

The final protocol for preparation of the individual full-length *nsp14* was as follows: The N-terminally tagged *nsp14* was expressed in *E. coli* Rossetta II in TB medium supplemented with ampicillin and chloramphenicol. Upon reaching the OD₆₀₀ of 0.5, the cell culture was cooled to 16 °C, and subsequently the expression was induced by adding IPTG at a final concentration of 0.4 mM. After incubating the cultures for another 18 h at 16 °C, the cells were harvested by centrifugation (3000 × g, 15 min).

The cell pellet was then resuspended in Lysis buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 4 mM MgCl₂, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 10 % (v:v) glycerol), supplemented with Thermo Scientific Halt Protease Inhibitor Cocktail and benzonase. The cells were then disrupted using a continuous high-pressure homogenizer at 1.9 kbar, followed by clarification by centrifugation. The *nsp14*-containing supernatant was then loaded on a HisTrap column in Lysis buffer. After loading the supernatant, the column was washed with High Salt buffer containing 1000 mM NaCl and returned to Lysis buffer. The second wash step was conducted using a Chaperone Removing Buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 10 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM ATP, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 10 % (v:v) glycerol). The captured *nsp14* was eluted by 500 mM imidazole, supplemented with HisMBP-3CPR in a 1:10 (w:w) ratio and dialysed against 3 litres of Dialysis buffer (20 mM Na-HEPES pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 4 mM MgCl₂, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 10 % (v:v) glycerol) for 16 h at 4 °C. The His-MBP tag, protease, and uncleaved construct were subsequently captured on a HisTrap column (Cytiva). The collected flow-through fraction was diluted to a final concentration of 50 mM NaCl and loaded on a HiTrap heparin column (Cytiva) in Heparin binding buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 50 mM NaCl, 4 mM MgCl₂, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 10 % (v:v) glycerol) at 1 ml/min. The bound proteins were then eluted with a NaCl gradient from 50 mM to 1000 mM. The fractions containing *nsp14* were pooled and loaded on a HiLoad 26/600 Superdex 200 pg column (Cytiva) in SEC buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 4 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM TCEP, 10 % (v:v) glycerol) for final purification. Following this step, the protein was concentrated to 1.22 mg/ml (20 μM), flash-frozen, and stored at -80 °C until use.

2.2.2. *nsp10*

GST-TEV-*nsp10* was expressed in *E. coli* BL21. The expression was induced by adding IPTG to a final concentration of 0.4 mM. After that, the expression continued for 18 h at 16 °C. The cells were then harvested by centrifugation (3000 × g, 15 min).

For isolation of the protein, the pellet was resuspended in Lysis buffer (50 mM Na-HEPES pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 10 % (v:v) glycerol). DNase and Thermo Scientific Halt Protease Inhibitor Cocktail were added before lysing the cells with a high-pressure homogenizer (ConstantSystem) at 1.9 kbar. The lysate was subsequently clarified and loaded onto a GSTrap Column (Cytiva). Subsequently, the bound proteins were eluted with a linear gradient of glutathione from 0 to 20 mM. Fractions containing the construct were pooled and supplemented with His-tagged TEV protease in a 1:10 (w:w) ratio. The mixture was then dialysed against 3 litres of Lysis buffer containing 30 mM imidazole for 16 h at 4 °C. After that, the sample was loaded on a HisTrap column (Cytiva) serially connected to a GSTrap column to remove the uncleaved GST-*nsp10* construct, the GST tag, and the protease. The flow-through fraction containing free *nsp10* was collected, concentrated, and loaded onto a HiLoad 26/600 Superdex 200 pg column (Cytiva) equilibrated in 20 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 10 % (v:v) glycerol. The final fractions with *nsp10* were pooled, concentrated to 3 mg/ml (200 μM), flash-frozen, and stored at -80 °C.

2.3. TBE-PAGE-based exoribonuclease activity assay

To monitor the exoribonuclease activity, nsp10 and nsp14 were initially mixed in the given ratios in the reaction buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 8.0, 10 mM KCl, 6 mM MgCl₂, 0.01 % Triton X-100, 1 mM DTT) and incubated for 15 min at room temperature. The reactions were then initiated by adding the FAM-labelled ssRNA (5'-FAM-GCUAUGUGA-GAUUAAGUUAUU-3'). The mixtures were incubated for the given time at 37 °C, after which the reactions were stopped by adding the Stop Solution (95 % Formamide, 0.02 % SDS, 10 mM EDTA). Mixtures were then analysed by PAGE in TBE buffer in a 10 % polyacrylamide gel.

For inhibitor testing, the molar ratio of 1:3 (nsp14:nsp10) was selected with final concentrations of 500 nM and 1500 nM, respectively. The time was set to 15 min to ensure that the reactions reached the endpoint.

Compounds exhibiting putative inhibitory activity were evaluated in two-fold serial dilutions from 500 µM to 15.6 µM to verify the inhibition and qualitatively assess the concentration-dependent behaviour.

2.4. Thermal stability assay

The initial evaluation of individual proteins and their mixtures in different molar ratios was conducted in the nsp14 SEC buffer. For compound testing, 2.5 µM nsp14 and 7.5 µM nsp10 were mixed in reaction buffer and incubated at room temperature for 15 min. Subsequently, tested compounds in DMSO were added to a final concentration of 50 µM and the whole mixture was incubated for another 15 min.

Thermal unfolding parameters were then determined employing nano-differential scanning fluorimetry (nanoDSF) using Prometheus Panta (Nanotemper). Mixtures were loaded into Prometheus Standard Capillaries (Nanotemper) and each sample was heated at 2 °C per minute from 25 to 95 °C while intrinsic fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 280$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 330$ and 350 nm) was monitored throughout the process. Results were analysed using the Panta Analysis Software (Nanotemper). The midpoint denaturation temperatures (T_M) were collected from inflection points within the fluorescence ratio (350/330 nm) curves.

Thermal shifts were calculated by subtracting the T_M of the control mixture with DMSO from the T_M of the mixture with a compound. The T_M of the ExoN complex in DMSO was determined with each compound set. All thermal stability experiments were conducted in two technical replicates and two biological replicates. The presented results represent the average ΔT_M between biological replicates \pm biological standard error of the mean (SEM_{BIO}).

2.5. FRET-based exoribonuclease activity assay

The FRET-based exoribonuclease activity assay was based on a previously published protocol [5]. To generate the dsRNA substrate, 5'-FAM-GGUAGUAAUCCGCUC-3' and 5'-UUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUUGAGCGGAUUACUACC-BHQ1-3' ssRNAs were mixed in a 1:1.2 molar ratio and heated at 95 °C for 3 min, after which the solution was slowly cooled to 4 °C. The reaction mixtures were then prepared by mixing nsp14 and nsp10 at final concentrations of 100 nM and 300 nM, respectively, in reaction buffer. To the 17 µl of reaction mixture, 1 µl of DMSO or compound solution was added. The exoribonuclease reaction was initiated by adding 2 µl of the dsRNA substrate, with the final concentration of the substrate being 500 nM. The mixtures were subsequently incubated at 22 °C for 50 min. QuantStudio 5 real-time PCR system (Applied Biosystems) was used to monitor the increase of fluorescence every 60 s.

2.6. Determination of IC₅₀

The fluorescence curves obtained using the FRET-based exoribonuclease activity assay were analysed in GraphPad Prism 10.0.0. Each IC₅₀ calculation was based on three technical replicates. For each curve,

the linear portion was fitted using simple linear regression to obtain the slope, representing the initial velocity of the reaction. The average initial velocity at each inhibitor concentration was then calculated together with the standard deviation. These values were subsequently normalized to the initial velocity of the control reaction without inhibitor, defined as 100 %. IC₅₀ values were then determined by fitting normalized activity data to a four-parameter logistic equation using the 'dose-response – inhibition' model in Prism:

$$Y = \frac{100}{10^{\text{HillSlope} \times (\log \text{IC}_{50} - X)} + 1}$$

where X is the logarithm of inhibitor concentration and Y is the normalized response, 100–0 %, decreasing as X increases. The reported IC₅₀ values represent the best-fit parameters with 95 % confidence intervals (95 % CI). The quality of each fit was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2).

2.7. Molecular docking

Protein structure of the ExoN domain of nsp14 (1 – 288) with nsp10 (PDB ID 7DIY [22]) was downloaded from <https://www.rcsb.org/>. The ligands – ellagic acid, myricetin, and hesperidin – were obtained from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/> in SDF format. Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock Vina [44,11] within the UCSF Chimera 1.17.3 software [35]. The docking grid was defined to cover the entire receptor, enabling unbiased evaluation of the binding site. Both the receptor and ligands were prepared using the built-in DockPrep tool, adding hydrogens, and assigning the charges with the Gasteiger method. Nine poses were generated for each docking experiment and evaluated using the Vina score. The best-scoring pose was subsequently visually inspected in the PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.5.4 (Schrödinger, LLC).

2.8. DSBU crosslinking

Crosslinking was performed to evaluate the hypothesis of shikonin-induced disruption of nsp14:nsp10 interaction. For this purpose, NHS-ester crosslinker DSBU (disuccinimidyl dibutyric urea; CF Plus Chemicals, Czech Republic) was utilized. All steps were performed at room temperature. Nsp14 at a final concentration of 10 µM was initially mixed with nsp10 in 1:1, 1:3, and 1:5 (nsp14:nsp10) molar ratios in reaction buffer. Subsequently, shikonin in DMSO was added to a final concentration of 50 µM. Control reactions were supplemented with DMSO only. All mixtures were incubated for an additional 15 min before adding freshly dissolved DSBU in DMSO to achieve a final molar ratio of 40:1 (crosslinker:nsp14). Reaction mixtures were incubated for 30 min and subsequently quenched by adding Tris Base to a final concentration of 50 mM. After the final 10-minute incubation, the mixtures were mixed with SDS loading buffer and analysed by SDS-PAGE on a 15 % acrylamide gel, followed by Coomassie staining. The crosslinking was qualitatively evaluated by the appearance and intensity of a band corresponding to nsp14:nsp10 crosslinked species.

2.9. Visualization

Plots were visualized in Graphpad Prism 10.0.0. For structural representation, a combination of the PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.5.4 (Schrödinger, LLC) and PLIP (<https://plip-tool.biotec.tu-dresden.de>) [40] was utilized. Schematic representations of enzyme assay designs and final figure assemblies were produced in BioRender (<https://www.biorender.com/>).

3. Results

3.1. Reconstitution of the SARS-CoV-2 ExoN complex *in vitro*

Previous research has highlighted the challenges associated with the production of nsp14, primarily due to the instability of the ExoN domain. Several strategies have been explored to overcome insufficient yields or low activity. These include co-expressing nsp14 with nsp10 or molecular chaperones [22,27,29,49], fusing nsp14 with nsp10 [5], or expressing exclusively the ExoN domain [2]. Our initial strategy was to co-express nsp14 with nsp10, using an N-terminal histidine tag fused to either maltose binding protein (MBP) or SUMO, in order to facilitate purification and stabilize the complex. Despite extensive optimization, this strategy yielded insufficient quantities of proteins. However, we developed a refined protocol that enabled the efficient production of nsp14 alone, thus eliminating the need for co-expression with nsp10. Our final protocol, adapted from Riccio et al.[37] with minor modifications, resulted in consistently high yields and satisfactory purity. Specifically, we introduced an additional washing step to remove bacterial chaperones and used a 3C protease carrying the same tag as nsp14, which was prepared specifically for this purpose. The detailed step-by-step procedure is described in the Methods section. Nsp10 was expressed separately using N-terminal fusion to glutathione-S-transferase (GST) and purified accordingly. Unlike Riccio et al.[37], we stored the proteins individually and reconstituted the ExoN complex before use (Fig. 1, A).

To evaluate the exoribonuclease activity, we used a simple TBE-PAGE-based assay to monitor the cleavage of a 20nt ssRNA substrate

labelled at the 5' end with FAM (Fig. 1, B), used at a concentration of 500 nM unless stated otherwise. Nsp14 alone exhibited no detectable activity, and the equimolar mixture of nsp10 and nsp14 showed limited cleavage (Fig. 1, C). Full catalytic activity was only observed when nsp14 was combined with nsp10 at a molar ratio of at least 1:3 (Fig. 1, D). This is consistent with previous research reporting that an excess of nsp10 over nsp14 is required due to the relatively low affinity of their interaction [20,37]. Using this 1:3 molar ratio (500 nM nsp14 and 1500 nM nsp10), we further monitored the time-dependent cleavage of the substrate RNA. Under these conditions, the RNA substrate was almost completely cleaved within 10 min (Fig. 1, E). For the subsequent evaluation of inhibitory activity, the reactions were incubated for 15 min to reach the endpoint.

3.2. Thermal stability assay (TSA) and assay validation using ATA

While enzyme activity assays provide valuable insight into the effects of inhibitors on catalysis, they do not directly evaluate ligand binding or the other ways in which a small molecule may affect the enzyme. To complement our analysis, we therefore implemented a thermal stability assay (TSA), a widely used approach in inhibitor screening and evaluation. By analysing protein stability in the presence of a ligand, TSA allows for the assessment of interactions independent of enzymatic function. In this study, we employed nano-differential scanning fluorimetry (nanoDSF), which detects changes in the intrinsic fluorescence of tryptophan and tyrosine residues during protein unfolding [26].

To ensure the correct interpretation of the results, we first assessed the stability of nsp10 and nsp14 proteins individually, followed by

Fig. 1. Enzyme activity of *in vitro* reconstituted SARS-CoV-2 exoribonuclease nsp14:nsp10 (A) SDS-PAGE analysis of individually purified nsp10 and nsp14. (B) Schematic representation of the ExoN activity assay evaluated by TBE-PAGE, where the cleavage of full-length FAM-labelled 20nt ssRNA (FL FAM-ssRNA) is monitored. (C) The ExoN activity at different concentrations (500 nM, 250 nM, 125 nM, 62.5 nM, 32.3 nM, and 15.6 nM) of the nsp14:nsp10 mixture at a 1:1 molar ratio. (D) The effect of increasing concentration of nsp10 on the ExoN activity. The positions of the FL FAM-ssRNA and of the cleavage products are marked. For evaluation of both the nsp14 concentration in (C) and nsp14:nsp10 molar ratio (D), the reactions were incubated for 15 min at 37 °C upon the addition of substrate RNA. (E) Assessment of the FL FAM-ssRNA cleavage over time with nsp14:nsp10 at a molar ratio of 1:3 (500 nM:1500 nM). The concentration of substrate FL-FAM-ssRNA in all experiments was 500 nM. NC (Negative control) = reaction mixture without either nsp14 or nsp10. “Nsp14” and “nsp10” mark lines with reaction mixtures containing only nsp14 or nsp10, respectively.

measuring the stability of their mixture at various molar ratios. The average midpoint denaturation temperatures (T_M) of nsp10 and nsp14 were 55.6 °C and 46.8 °C, respectively (Fig. 2, A, B, blue and red lines). The mixtures of nsp14 and nsp10 were analysed at molar ratios ranging from 1:1–1:10. For the 1:1 mixture, two distinct T_M values were identified (Fig. 2, A, B green line). This presumably reflects the abundance of free proteins not incorporated into the ExoN complex. Conversely, all the mixtures containing at least a 2.5-fold molar excess of nsp10 (Fig. 2, A, violet dotted line) exhibited an unfolding profile with a single T_M ranging around 53.4 °C. This T_M remained unchanged when the nsp10 concentration was further increased. As expected, the cumulative T_M was higher than that of nsp14 alone. This indicated that TSA could be used not only to identify molecules capable of stabilization, but also to identify compounds that disrupt or prevent the formation of the ExoN complex. To ensure consistency with the exoribonuclease activity assay, a molar ratio of 1:3 (nsp14:nsp10) was selected for subsequent TSA screening.

Prior to compound testing, both established assays were validated using ATA, a known ExoN inhibitor (Fig. 2, C). Consistent with previous studies, ATA demonstrated potent inhibitory effects (Fig. 2, E). At a

concentration of 20 μM , the ExoN activity was completely suppressed. In the TSA evaluation, ATA caused only a modest change in the T_M of the complex compared to the DMSO control. The maximum increase in T_M was approximately 1 °C. Nevertheless, the T_M increased gradually in a concentration-dependent manner, reaching a plateau at 100 μM ATA (Fig. 2, D). This concentration corresponded to a 1:20 molar ratio of nsp14 to ATA, and was used for subsequent TSA testing of the compound panel.

3.3. Dual-assay evaluation: TSA and enzyme activity inhibition

Following the validation of both assays for inhibitor testing, we screened the selected compound panel. As ATA only induced slight thermal stabilization, despite strongly inhibiting the ExoN activity, we first employed the TSA as a pre-screening test. Based on the results obtained with ATA, we tested each compound at a final concentration of 50 μM with 2.5 μM ExoN complex. In all cases, we collected the first inflection point as the representative T_M , enabling us to identify both destabilizing and stabilizing compounds (Fig. 3, A). Some of the stabilizing compounds, including flavone, myricetin, morin, mompoin,

Fig. 2. Thermal stability of ExoN and evaluation of aurintricarboxylic acid (ATA) (A) Upper panel shows the denaturation curves for nsp10, nsp14, and their mixtures (color coded) determined by nano-differential scanning fluorimetry. The denaturation course is represented as the fluorescence ratio at 350 nm and 330 nm. The lower panel shows the first derivative of the curves, indicating the position of inflection points i.e., mid-point denaturation temperatures (T_M). The violet dotted line represents a ratio and an inflection point of the lowest nsp14:nsp10 molar ratio that exhibits a single-inflection-point denaturation profile. (B) Plotted mid-point denaturation temperatures from (A). Two melting temperatures identified at the 1:1 molar ratio of nsp14:nsp10 are coded by color shades. (C) Chemical structure of aurintricarboxylic Acid (ATA). (D) Shifts of the T_M of nsp14:nsp10 mixture at a molar ratio of 1:3 induced by ATA at different concentrations. Plotted points were fitted with a simple non-linear regression to indicate concentration-dependent behavior. All thermal denaturation experiments were carried out at least in two technical replicates. (E) Evaluation of inhibitory effects of ATA using the TBE-PAGE-based exonuclease assay. ATA was added in two-fold serial dilutions, resulting in final concentrations of 160, 80, 40, 20, 10, 5, and 2.5 μM . All reaction mixtures were incubated for 15 min. NC (Negative control) represents the reaction mixture without the exonuclease and PC (Positive control) marks the reaction without either ATA or DMSO.

Fig. 3. Results of thermal shift assay and nuclease activity assay for selected compounds (A) Changes in the first midpoint denaturation temperature (ΔT_M) relative to the control nsp14:nsp10 mixture (molar ratio = 1:3) in DMSO. Values for compounds exhibiting a ΔT_M of at least

1 °C are presented, including both destabilizing (red) and stabilizing (blue) molecules. (B) Evaluation of concentration-dependent inhibition of nsp14:nsp10 exonuclease by selected compounds (myricetin, ellagic acid and shikonin). The compounds were added in two-fold dilutions, resulting in final concentrations of 500 nM, 250 nM, 125 nM, 62.5 nM, 32.3 nM, and 15.6 nM. NC represents a negative control without the enzyme and PC is a positive control reaction in the presence of DMSO. (C) Chemical structures of the selected compounds exhibiting inhibitory potency in (B).

chrysophanic acid, lapachol, and flavanone, exhibited larger thermal shifts (approximately + 1.5 – 3 °C) than ATA. Conversely, several molecules destabilized the complex. These included shikonin, apigenin, quambalerine B, luteolin, usnic acid, and emodin, which exhibited a shift of T_M ranging from – 1.8 to – 6.3 °C. Cynaroside exhibited the greatest impact on the T_M of ExoN complex, reducing it by approximately 7 °C compared to the control sample. The results for all compounds are presented in Table S2.

Subsequently, we evaluated all compounds for inhibitory activity in the TBE-PAGE-based exoribonuclease assay. Although a FRET-based assay was employed later in this study, we chose the lower-capacity TBE-PAGE assay for initial assessment, reasoning that it might provide more reliable results, as several compounds in the panel could interfere with fluorescence-based measurement. To further minimize the risk of false-positive hits, we included Triton X-100 and fresh DTT in the assay buffer. The testing was conducted with the compounds at a final concentration of 50 μM , and each result was compared with a solvent-only control (Fig. S1). Due to assay interference observed in the initial assessment, myricetin, luteolin, and morin were retested. The

compounds with apparent impact on RNA cleavage were further evaluated at different final concentrations to verify their inhibitory activity. This subset included phloroglucinol, ferullic acid, galangin, myricetin, ellagic acid, and shikonin. Among these, only three molecules exhibited measurable inhibitory activity against ExoN (Fig. 3, B, C). While ellagic acid and shikonin exhibited clear inhibitory activity, myricetin was a substantially weaker inhibitor. Cleavage efficiency decreased only at a myricetin concentration of 500 μM , as indicated by a small increase of signal in the “uncleaved RNA” region (Fig. 3, B upper panel).

3.4. Inhibitory potency of selected compounds

As a final step, we aimed to quantify the inhibitory potency by using real-time monitoring of substrate cleavage catalysed by ExoN. For this reason, we adapted a fluorometric ExoN activity assay published by Canal et al. [5], by utilizing a different fluorophore-quencher combination (Fig. 4, A). This assay is based on the fluorophore dissociation from the quencher upon cleavage of the shorter RNA strand. This enables real-time monitoring of the increase in fluorescence intensity,

Fig. 4. Inhibitory potency quantification for selected compounds utilizing a FRET-based assay (A) Schematic representation of the FRET-based exonuclease assay design using a combination of FAM (green) and BHQ1 (black) labelled RNA strands. (B) Fluorescence curves showing exonuclease activity in the FRET-based assay at different ATA concentrations (color-coded). Dotted lines indicate the standard deviation for each ATA concentration. (C) Calculated IC_{50} values for ATA based on initial velocities derived from fluorescence curves in (B). (D) IC_{50} values for the three selected compounds. IC_{50} values were determined by non-linear regression using GraphPad Prism 10. All presented results were measured in three technical replicates. 95 % CI (95 % confidence interval) represents the profile likelihood, which is the interval that contains the IC_{50} value with 95 % confidence. RFU = Relative Fluorescence Units.

which directly reflects the exoribonuclease activity. Notably, previous research has shown that double-stranded RNA with a 5' end overhang is the optimal ExoN substrate [8], making the assay more biologically relevant.

The evaluation of inhibitory parameters using enzymatic activity assays is highly dependent on reaction conditions and may also vary with different protein production protocols. To compare our data with those reported for previously described inhibitors, we determined the IC_{50} of ATA. Under our experimental conditions, ATA exhibited a strong inhibitory effect with an IC_{50} equal to $1.14 \mu\text{M}$ (95 % CI $0.88 - 1.50 \mu\text{M}$) (Fig. 4, C). Next, we analysed three compounds previously identified through the TBE-PAGE-based exoribonuclease assay. As anticipated, myricetin and ellagic acid exhibited rather poor inhibitory potency, with myricetin being 125 times less potent than ATA. The determined IC_{50} values for these compounds were $142 \mu\text{M}$ (95 % CI $106 - 205 \mu\text{M}$) and $44.4 \mu\text{M}$ (95 % CI $37.5 - 52.9 \mu\text{M}$), respectively (Fig. 4, D). Among the tested compounds, shikonin was the strongest inhibitor, as evidenced by an IC_{50} equal to $7.92 \mu\text{M}$ (95 % CI $6.95 - 9.03 \mu\text{M}$). Nevertheless, its inhibitory activity was still sevenfold lower than that of ATA (Fig. 4, D).

3.5. Mechanistic insight into the inhibitory activity of selected compounds

Despite their limited inhibitory potency, the TSA results indicated that both ellagic acid and myricetin could act as direct binders (Fig. 3, A Tab. S2), stabilizing the ExoN complex with T_M shifts of $+1.19 \pm 0.30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $+2.52 \pm 1.57 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. To provide a structural model and compare the experimental results with the computational predictions, we performed a simple global docking using the exonuclease domain of nsp14 in complex with nsp10 and a single magnesium ion in the active site (PDB ID 7DIY [22]) (Fig. 5, A). The most plausible models posed both ellagic acid (Fig. 5, B) and myricetin (Fig. 5, C) into the active site, in contact with surrounding residues, with the predicted binding energies favouring ellagic acid (Table 1). As a control, we re-docked hesperidin (Fig. S3), a compound that has been previously suggested as a strong ExoN binder [19], but which was found to be inactive in our experimental assay (Fig. S1). Docking positioned hesperidin within the active site pocket with an even stronger predicted binding score, contradicting its lack of inhibitory activity.

Shikonin, the most potent inhibitor among the panel, was identified as a slightly destabilizing compound in the TSA screen, with ΔT_M

Fig. 5. Indications of mode of action for selected compounds (A) Model of the exonuclease domain of nsp14 (wheat) bound to nsp10 (green) (PDB ID 7DIY). The magnesium ion (gray sphere) is coordinated by the active site residues. (B) Predicted binding pose of ellagic acid within the nsp14 active site. (C) Docking pose of myricetin within the same pocket. Both (B) and (C) represent the best-scoring poses of global molecular docking performed with AutoDock Vina within the UCSF Chimera interface on the nsp14 exonuclease domain bound to nsp10 (PDB ID 7DIY) visualized using PLIP (<https://plip-tool.biotec.tu-dresden.de/plip-web/plip/index>) and the PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.5.4 (Schrödinger, LLC). The experiment was performed both with and without Mg^{2+} , where the presence of the Mg^{2+} ion yielded more reliable poses. Interacting residues are visualized in marine blue along with their respective interactions (blue – hydrogen bond, gray – hydrophobic interactions, green – π - π stacking with light gray spheres showing the aromatic ring centers). (D) Representation of nsp14:nsp10 interaction interface in cartoon; red – interacting regions in nsp10, blue – interface residues in nsp14. (E) SDS-PAGE analysis of nsp14 (~61 kDa) and nsp10 (~15 kDa) crosslinked in the presence of shikonin. Comparison of DMSO and shikonin-treated samples qualitatively shows disruption of the ExoN complex (~76 kDa) and increased intensity of the 30 kDa band, likely representing the nsp10 homodimer. All samples contained 2 % DMSO. No DSBU represents the control sample; the concentration of shikonin was 50 μ M with DSBU added in a 40:1 molar ratio (DSBU:nsp14).

$= -1.82 \pm 1.20$. Furthermore, the thermal denaturation profile in the presence of shikonin resembled that of free nsp14 (cf. Fig. S2 blue line and Fig. 2, A red line), with the signal corresponding to nsp10 or the nsp14:nsp10 complex being completely absent. Based on these results, we hypothesized that shikonin may disrupt the interaction between nsp14 and nsp10, characterized by a broad interface spanning substantial portions of both proteins (Fig. 5, D). Instead of modelling the

shikonin binding, we therefore performed a crosslinking experiment with nsp14 and nsp10. In the absence of shikonin, the analysis revealed a ~76 kDa band corresponding to the ExoN complex (Fig. 5, E). Treatment with shikonin markedly reduced the abundance of this band and increased the intensity of a band just above 30 kDa, likely representing the nsp10 homodimer, which is functionally inactive [38]. Thus, shikonin represents a promising compound for deeper

Table 1

Summary of inhibitory activity and molecular docking results for selected compounds.

Compound	Docking score [kcal.mol ⁻¹]*	IC ₅₀ [μM]**	Interacting residues
Ellagic Acid	- 8.0	44.4 (95 % CI 37.5 - 52.9)	Hydrophobic: F190 Hydrogen bonds: G93, N104, A187, G198, F190 π-π stacking: F190
Myricetin	- 6.9	142 (95 % CI 106 - 205)	Hydrophobic: F190 Hydrogen bonds: E92, G93, N104, L253, H268
Hesperidin	- 8.4	no activity	Hydrophobic: F190 Hydrogen bonds: G93, N104, G189, N252, N266 Salt bridges: H268

*The Docking scores are presented as qualitative trends rather than absolute affinity predictions. **95 % CI is the 95 % confidence interval.

structure-functional analysis, which could provide valuable insights for the rational design of novel inhibitors with a similar mode of action.

4. Discussion

The proofreading mediated by ExoN in CoVs represents a vital target for novel antivirals due to its essential role in maintaining the fidelity of RNA synthesis and potentially serving as a resistance factor against nucleoside analogues. While numerous computational studies have explored the possibilities of ExoN inhibition, often emphasizing the potential of natural phenolic compounds, their experimental validation has been limited. Furthermore, despite extensive efforts employing various strategies for discovering new ExoN inhibitors, no efficient and specific compound has yet been identified.

In this study, we employed a dual-assay approach combining TSA and ExoN activity assay to evaluate a panel of phenolic compounds. This orthogonal strategy not only enhances confidence in obtained hits but may also provide mechanistic insight, helping to eliminate false-positive hits. However, it is important to note that TSA results do not necessarily correlate with inhibitory potency, as it was shown that some inhibitors do not trigger a significant change in thermal stability [39]. It is also relevant to emphasize that we used a full-length nsp14. Therefore, observed thermal effects could arise from interactions with the methyltransferase domain, which could leave the ExoN domain unaffected. Furthermore, the TSA evaluation was performed in the absence of the substrate RNA, which likely alters the dynamics of the ExoN complex. Molecular dynamics simulations proposed that RNA binding reduces the flexibility of both nsp14 and nsp10 [29], whereas the cryo-EM structure also showed a stable binding of RNA to the ExoN complex [24]. Consequently, some effects observed in the absence of RNA may not be significant under conditions when RNA is present.

The screening panel contained compounds highlighted in previous *in silico* studies as potential ExoN inhibitors ([18,19,10][25,31,45]). However, most of these compounds failed to demonstrate inhibitory activity, indicating a poor correlation between the *in silico* prediction and experimental evaluation. For instance, hesperidin was proposed as an effective ligand targeting the ExoN active site, potentially preventing substrate binding. Furthermore, molecular dynamics simulation showed that hesperidin potentially binds to all five catalytic residues while remaining stable within the active site [19]. While TSA revealed a slight hesperidin-mediated stabilization of the ExoN complex (Tab. S2), it did not inhibit the catalytic activity. Moreover, the molecular docking validation also suggested a strong binding of hesperidin to the ExoN active site (Table 1 and Fig. S3). These observations illustrate that while molecular docking can provide reasonable binding models when supported by experimental validation (Fig. 5, B and C), the scoring-function-driven hypotheses alone are insufficient to demonstrate inhibition (Table 1).

We also tested several coumarin derivatives, along with precursors of procyanidins, emodin, or baicalein, based on the molecular docking results reported in the study by De et al. De et al., [10]. Nevertheless, none of these compounds exhibited inhibitory effects against ExoN, including baicalein, despite earlier reports suggesting its potential inhibitory effect on ExoN (C. [25]). Apart from baicalein, some other flavonoids and their glycosides have been explored as potential ExoN inhibitors [18,31]. In our dual-assay evaluation, we included 20 flavonoid representatives from different classes. Among these, only myricetin exhibited measurable inhibitory activity, which aligns with previous reports [6]. Compounds selected for their chelating bioactivities [1], such as caffeic acid or ferulic acid, were also unable to inhibit ExoN under the tested conditions.

To compare and contextualize the identified hits, we included ATA, a confirmed SARS-CoV-2 ExoN inhibitor, in the dual-assay evaluation. Reported IC₅₀ values for ATA include 7.6 ± 1.2 μM for 100 nM copurified nsp14 and nsp10 [3], and 8.6–12.1 μM for 0.5 nM nsp10-nsp14 fusion protein [5]. These values are consistent with our estimates, which were obtained using the TBE-PAGE-based exoribonuclease assay for nsp14:nsp10 complex (Fig. 2, E). On the contrary, the IC₅₀ obtained through the FRET-based assay was lower, reaching 1.14 μM. We hypothesize that this discrepancy may be due to the following factors: a lower reaction temperature, a reduced final enzyme concentration (100 nM nsp14 and 300 nM nsp10), and the use of dsRNA rather than ssRNA [27,29]. All of these modifications can alter enzymatic activity, thereby affecting the determined inhibitory potency. When compared to the IC₅₀ values reported for the established ATA inhibitor, both ellagic acid and myricetin demonstrated negligible inhibitory potency. The structural models of these two compounds (Fig. 5, B and C) indicated that in addition to certain active site residues (i.e., Asp90, Glu92, Glu191, His268, and Asp273) and magnesium ion coordination [22], Phe190 and Asn104 may also contribute to the binding of these molecules within the active site pocket. At the same time, experimental validation shows that targeting the ExoN active site may be difficult.

None of the tested compounds matched the potency of previously described inhibitors such as ebselen, with an IC₅₀ equal to 3.30 ± 0.09 μM [3]. However, we believe that shikonin possesses interesting implications for future drug design, despite its IC₅₀ lying in the double-digit micromolar range. Shikonin has been extensively studied as an antiviral due to its inhibitory activity against the Main protease of CoVs [17,50,9], but not with regard to ExoN inhibition. Notably, the use of TSA and subsequent crosslinking validation (Fig. 5, E) revealed a novel mode of action for shikonin, involving the disruption of the ExoN complex. Furthermore, the TSA results (Fig. 3, A) suggested that shikonin may target nsp10, since neither nsp10 nor the ExoN complex exhibited a typical unfolding profile (Fig. S2). The unfolding transition of nsp10 in nanoDSF is likely dominated by the single tryptophan residue at position 123, which is normally buried within the protein core [38]. Any interaction affecting this residue could thus lead to significant changes in the observed denaturation profile. We also believe that the observed effect of shikonin does not result from non-specific inhibition caused by colloidal aggregation [36], since other compounds with similar or even higher aggregation index (logP) did not affect the ExoN activity. Furthermore, both detergent and freshly prepared DTT were included in the TSA and exoribonuclease activity assays. Intriguingly, Canal et al. [5] also tested shikonin in their HTS screen for ExoN inhibitors using an nsp10-nsp14 fusion construct; however, it did not appear among their top hits. This highlights the potential of orthogonal approaches such as TSA to uncover context-dependent inhibitors and underscores the importance of further investigation of shikonin's mode of action.

In conclusion, identifying inhibitors of the SARS-CoV-2 ExoN remains challenging. To the best of our knowledge, no study has reported any inhibitor with a sub-micromolar IC₅₀ value against this enzyme. However, shikonin represents a promising candidate for investigating

small molecules that interfere with the dynamic interaction between nsp14 and nsp10. The interaction between nsp14 and nsp10 is rather complex (Fig. 5, D) and involves significant conformational changes within the ExoN domain of nsp14 [15]. Moreover, nsp10 is also a cofactor of nsp16 methyltransferase, which is involved in RNA capping with studies indicating a complex interplay between nsp10, nsp14, and nsp16 [28]. While the high cytotoxicity of shikonin likely prevents its direct use [17], it still represents a useful starting point for exploring the nsp14:nsp10 interaction disruptors. For this reason, an in-depth structural investigation and identification of hotspots for such small molecules represent a promising pathway towards discovering novel inhibitors as an alternative to the classical active site binders.

Abbreviations used

95 % CI 95 % confidence interval
 ATA aurintricarboxylic acid
 BHQ1 black hole quencher 1
 COVID-19 coronavirus disease 2019
 CoV scoronaviruses
 DMSO dimethylsulfoxide
 DSBU disuccinimidyl dibutyric urea
 DTT dithiotreitol
 ExoN exoribonuclease
 FAM fluorescein
 FRET fluorescence resonance energy transfer
 GST glutathione-S-transferase
 IC₅₀ half-maximal inhibitory concentration
 MBP maltose binding protein
 nanoDSF nano-differential scanning fluorimetry
 nsp non-structural protein
 RTC replication-transcription complex
 SARS-CoV-2 Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome 2
 SUMO small ubiquitin-like modifier
 TBE-PAGE Tris/Borate/EDTA polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
 TEV protease Tobacco Etch Virus protease
 TSA thermal shift assay

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chvátalová Barbora: Methodology, Data curation. **Danda Matěj:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nečasová Daniela:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Ruml Tomáš:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Křížová Ivana:** Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Rumláková Michaela:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2025.118588.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] M. AAlikhani, M. Khalili, M. Jahanshahi, The natural iron chelators' ferulic acid and caffeic acid rescue mice's brains from side effects of iron overload, *Front. Neurol.* 13 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2022.951725>.
- [2] A. Asthana, A. Corona, W.J. Shin, M.J. Kwak, C. Gaughan, E. Tramontano, J. U. Jung, R. Schobert, B.K. Jha, R.H. Silverman, B. Biersack, Analogs of the catechol derivative dynasore inhibit HIV-1 ribonuclease H, SARS-CoV-2 nsp14 exoribonuclease, and virus replication, *Viruses* 15 (7) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/v15071539>.
- [3] H.T. Baddock, S. Broluh, Y. Yosaatmadja, M. Ratnaweera, M. Bielinski, L.P. Swift, A. Cruz-Migoni, H.T. Fan, J.R. Keown, A.P. Walker, G.M. Morris, J.M. Grimes, E. Fodor, C.J. Schofield, O. Gileadi, P.J. McHugh, Characterization of the SARS-CoV-2 ExoN (nsp14-nsp10) complex: implications for its role in viral genome stability and inhibitor identification, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 50 (3) (2022) 1484–1500, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkabl303>.
- [4] M. Bouvet, I. Imbert, L. Subissi, L. Gluais, B. Canard, E. Decroly, RNA 3'-end mismatch excision by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus nonstructural protein nsp10/nsp14 exoribonuclease complex, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 109 (24) (2012) 9372–9377, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1201130109>.
- [5] B. Canal, A.W. McClure, J.F. Curran, M. Wu, R. Ulferts, F. Weissmann, J. Zeng, A. P. Bertolin, J.C. Milligan, S. Basu, L.S. Drury, T.D. Deegan, R. Fujisawa, E. L. Roberts, C. Basier, K. Labib, R. Beale, M. Howell, J.F.X. Diffley, Identifying SARS-CoV-2 antiviral compounds by screening for small molecule inhibitors of nsp14/nsp10 exoribonuclease, *Biochem. J.* 478 (13) (2021) 2445–2464, <https://doi.org/10.1042/bcj20210198>.
- [6] O.A. Chaves, N. Fintelman-Rodrigues, X. Wang, C.Q. Sacramento, J.R. Temerozo, A.C. Ferreira, M. Mattos, F. Pereira-Dutra, P.T. Bozza, H.C. Castro-Faria-Neto, J. J. Russo, J. Ju, T.M.L. Souza, Commercially available flavonols are better SARS-CoV-2 inhibitors than isoflavone and flavones, *Viruses* 14 (7) (2022).
- [7] T. Chen, C.Y. Fei, Y.P. Chen, K. Sargsyan, C.P. Chang, H.S. Yuan, C. Lim, Synergistic inhibition of SARS-CoV-2 replication using Disulfiram/Ebselen and remdesivir, *ACS Pharmacol. Transl. Sci.* 4 (2) (2021) 898–907, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acspsci.1c00022>.
- [8] T.L. Dangerfield, K.A. Johnson, Substrate specificity and kinetics of RNA hydrolysis by SARS-CoV-2 NSP10/14 exonuclease, *ACS Bio Med Chem. Au* 2 (6) (2022) 600–606, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbiochem.2c00046>.
- [9] R. Das, S.U. Habiba, R. Dash, Y. Seo, J. Woo, Unveiling the potentiality of shikonin derivatives inhibiting SARS-CoV-2 main protease by molecular dynamic simulation studies, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24 (4) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24043100>.
- [10] A. De, S. Bhattacharya, B. Debroy, A. Bhattacharya, K. Pal, Exploring the pharmacological aspects of natural phytochemicals against SARS-CoV-2 Nsp14 through an in silico approach, *Silico Pharmacol.* 11 (1) (2023) 12, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40203-023-00143-7>.
- [11] J. Eberhardt, D. Santos-Martins, A.F. Tillack, S. Forli, AutoDock vina 1.2.0: new docking methods, expanded force field, and python bindings, *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* 61 (8) (2021) 3891–3898, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.1c00203>.
- [12] K.C. Figueredo, C.G. Guex, J. Graiczik, F.Z. Reginato, A.M. Engelmann, C.M. De Andrade, L.F.S.M. Timmers, L.D. Bauermann, Caffeic acid and ferulic acid can improve toxicological damage caused by iron overload mediated by carbonic anhydrase inhibition, *Drug Chem. Toxicol.* 47 (2) (2024) 147–155, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01480545.2022.2152043>.
- [13] Q. Hanson, X. Hu, S. Pal, K. Recabo, L. Ye, I. Poon, J.-P. Denson, S. Messing, M. Shen, K.M. Wilson, A. Zakharov, D. Esposito, N.J. Martinez, A High-Throughput screening pipeline to identify methyltransferase and exonuclease inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 NSP14, *Biochemistry* 64 (2) (2025) 419–431, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biochem.4c00490>.
- [14] S. Hernandez, M. Feracci, C.T. De Jesus, P. El Kazzi, R. Kaci, L. Garlatti, C. Mondielli, F. Bailly, P. Cotellet, F. Touret, X. de Lamballerie, B. Coutard, E. Decroly, B. Canard, F. Ferron, K. Alvarez, Identification of potent inhibitors of arenavirus and SARS-CoV-2 exoribonucleases by fluorescence polarization assay, *Antivir. Res.* 204 (2022) 105364, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.antiviral.2022.105364>.
- [15] N. Imprachim, Y. Yosaatmadja, J.A. Newman, Crystal structures and fragment screening of SARS-CoV-2 NSP14 reveal details of exoribonuclease activation and mRNA capping and provide starting points for antiviral drug development, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 51 (1) (2023) 475–487, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1207>.
- [16] Z.S. Jiang, Q.D. You, X.J. Zhang, Medicinal chemistry of metal chelating fragments in metalloenzyme active sites: a perspective, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 165 (2019) 172–197, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2019.01.018>.
- [17] Z.M. Jin, X.Y. Du, Y.C. Xu, Y.Q. Deng, M.Q. Liu, Y. Zhao, B. Zhang, X.F. Li, L. K. Zhang, C. Peng, Y.K. Duan, J. Yu, L. Wang, K.L. Yang, F.J. Liu, R.D. Jiang, X. L. Yang, T. You, X.C. Liu, H.T. Yang, Structure of mpro from SARS-CoV-2 and

- discovery of its inhibitors, *Nature* 582 (7811) (2020) 289, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2223-y>.
- [18] S. Khan, A. Hussain, Y. Vahdani, H. Kooshki, B. Mahmud Hussien, S. Haghghat, M. Fatih Rasul, H. Jamal Hidayat, A. Hasan, Z. Edis, S. Haj Bloukh, S. Kasravi, M. Mahdi Nejadi Babadaei, M. Sharifi, Q. Bai, J. Liu, B. Hu, K. Akhtari, M. Falahati, Exploring the interaction of quercetin 3-O-sophoroside with SARS-CoV-2 main proteins by theoretical studies: a probable prelude to control some variants of coronavirus including delta, *Arab. J. Chem.* 14 (10) (2021) 103353, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabj.2021.103353>.
- [19] S. Khater, P. Kumar, N. Dasgupta, G. Das, S. Ray, A. Prakash, Combining SARS-CoV-2 proofreading exonuclease and RNA-Dependent RNA polymerase inhibitors as a strategy to combat COVID-19: a High-Throughput in silico screening [Original Research], *Front. Microbiol.* 12 (2021). (<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2021.647693>).
- [20] F. Kozielski, C. Sele, V.O. Talibov, J.Q. Lou, D.N. Dong, Q. Wang, X.Y. Shi, M. Nyblom, A. Rogstam, T. Krojer, Z. Fisher, W. Knecht, Identification of fragments binding to SARS-CoV-2 nsp10 reveals ligand-binding sites in conserved interfaces between nsp10 and nsp14/nsp16, *RSC Chem. Biol.* 3 (1) (2022) 44–55, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1cb00135c>.
- [21] G.D. Li, R. Hilgenfeld, R. Whitley, E. De Clercq, Therapeutic strategies for COVID-19: progress and lessons learned, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 22 (6) (2023) 449–475, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41573-023-00672-y>.
- [22] S. Lin, H. Chen, Z. Chen, F. Yang, F. Ye, Y. Zheng, J. Yang, X. Lin, H. Sun, L. Wang, A. Wen, H. Dong, Q. Xiao, D. Deng, Y. Cao, G. Lu, Crystal structure of SARS-CoV-2 nsp10 bound to nsp14-ExoN domain reveals an exonuclease with both structural and functional integrity, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 49 (9) (2021) 5382–5392, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab320>.
- [23] E. Lionta, G. Spyrou, D.K. Vassiliatis, Z. Cournia, Structure-Based virtual screening for drug discovery: principles, applications and recent advances, *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* 14 (16) (2014) 1923–1938, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568026614666140929124445>.
- [24] C. Liu, W. Shi, S.T. Becker, D.G. Schatz, B. Liu, Y. Yang, Structural basis of mismatch recognition by a SARS-CoV-2 proofreading enzyme, *Science* 373 (6559) (2021) 1142–1146, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abi9310>.
- [25] C. Liu, X.X. Zhu, Y.Y. Lu, X.Q. Zhang, X. Jia, T. Yang, Potential treatment with Chinese and Western Medicine targeting NSP14 of SARS-CoV-2, *J. Pharm. Anal.* 11 (3) (2021) 272–277, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpha.2020.08.002>.
- [26] P. Llowarch, L. Usselman, D. Ivanov, G.A. Holdgate, Thermal unfolding methods in drug discovery, *Biophys. Rev. (Melville)* 4 (2) (2023) 021305, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0144141>.
- [27] Z. Ma, Y. Pourfarjam, I.-K. Kim, Reconstitution and functional characterization of SARS-CoV-2 proofreading complex, *Protein Expr. Purif.* 185 (2021) 105894, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pep.2021.105894>.
- [28] A. Matsuda, J. Plewka, M. Rawski, A. Mourao, W. Zajko, T. Siebenmorgen, L. Kresik, K. Lis, A.N. Jones, M. Pachota, A. Karim, K. Hartman, S. Nirwal, R. Sonani, Y. Chykunova, I. Minia, P. Mak, M. Landthaler, M. Nowotny, A. Czarna, Despite the odds: formation of the SARS-CoV-2 methylation complex, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 52 (11) (2024) 6441–6458, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae165>.
- [29] N.H. Moeller, K. Shi, O. Demir, C. Belica, S. Banerjee, L. Yin, C. Durfee, R.E. Amaro, H. Aihara, Structure and dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 proofreading exonuclease ExoN, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 119 (9) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2106379119>.
- [30] E.N. Muratov, R. Amaro, C.H. Andrade, N. Brown, S. Ekins, D. Fouches, O. Isayev, D. Kozakov, J.L. Medina-Franco, K.M. Merz, T. Oprea, V. Poroiikov, G. Schneider, M.H. Todd, A. Varnek, D.A. Winkler, A. Zakharov, A. Cherkasov, A. Tropsha, A critical overview of computational approaches employed for COVID-19 drug discovery, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 50 (16) (2021) 9121–9151, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0cs01065k>.
- [31] B. Naik, N. Gupta, R. Ojha, S. Singh, V.K. Prajapati, D. Prusty, High throughput virtual screening reveals SARS-CoV-2 multi-target binding natural compounds to lead instant therapy for COVID-19 treatment, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 160 (2020) 1–17, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.05.184>.
- [32] N.S. Ogando, J.C. Zevenhoven-Dobbe, Y. van der Meer, P.J. Bredenbeek, C. Posthuma, E.J. Snijder, The enzymatic activity of the nsp14 exonuclease is critical for replication of MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2, *J. Virol.* 94 (23) (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01246-20>.
- [33] K. Park, A review of computational drug repurposing, *Transl. Clin. Pharm.* 27 (2) (2019) 59–63, <https://doi.org/10.12793/tcp.2019.27.2.59>.
- [34] M. Pavan, S. Moro, Lessons learnt from COVID-19: computational strategies for facing present and future pandemics, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24 (5) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24054401>.
- [35] E.F. Pettersen, T.D. Goddard, C.C. Huang, G.S. Couch, D.M. Greenblatt, E.C. Meng, T.E. Ferrin, UCSF chimera - a visualization system for exploratory research and analysis, *J. Comput. Chem.* 25 (13) (2004) 1605–1612, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.20084>.
- [36] D. Reker, G.J.L. Bernardes, T. Rodrigues, Computational advances in combating colloidal aggregation in drug discovery, *Nat. Chem.* 11 (5) (2019) 402–418, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41557-019-0234-9>.
- [37] A.A. Riccio, E.D. Sullivan, W.C. Copeland, Activation of the SARS-CoV-2 NSP14 3'-5' exonuclease by NSP10 and response to antiviral inhibitors, *J. Biol. Chem.* 298 (1) (2022) 101518, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbc.2021.101518>.
- [38] A. Rogstam, M. Nyblom, S. Christensen, C. Sele, V.O. Talibov, T. Lindvall, A. A. Rasmussen, I. André, Z. Fisher, W. Knecht, F. Kozielski, Crystal structure of Non-Structural protein 10 from severe acute respiratory syndrome Coronavirus-2, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 21 (19) (2020), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21197375>.
- [39] G. Rona, A. Zeke, B. Miwatani-Minter, M. de Vries, R. Kaur, A. Schinlever, S. F. Garcia, H.V. Goldberg, H. Wang, T.R. Hinds, F. Bailly, N. Zheng, P. Cotelle, D. Desmaele, N.R. Landau, M. Dittmann, M. Pagano, The NSP14/NSP10 RNA repair complex as a Pan-coronavirus therapeutic target, *Cell Death Differ.* 29 (2) (2022) 285–292, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41418-021-00900-1>.
- [40] P. Schake, S.N. Bolz, K. Linnemann, M. Schroeder, PLIP 2025: introducing protein-protein interactions to the protein-ligand interaction profiler, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 53 (W1) (2025) W463–W465, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf361>.
- [41] F. Shahidi, P. Ambigaipalan, Phenolics and polyphenolics in foods, beverages and spices: antioxidant activity and health effects - a review, *J. Funct. Foods* 18 (2015) 820–897, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2015.06.018>.
- [42] E.C. Smith, H. Blanc, M. Vignuzzi, M.R. Denison, Coronaviruses lacking exonuclease activity are susceptible to lethal mutagenesis: evidence for proofreading and potential therapeutics, *PLOS Pathog.* 9 (8) (2013) e1003565, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1003565>.
- [43] M. Tahir, Coronavirus genomic nsp14-ExoN, structure, role, mechanism, and potential application as a drug target, *J. Med Virol.* 93 (7) (2021) 4258–4264, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27009>.
- [44] O. Trott, A.J. Olson, Software news and update AutoDock vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization, and multithreading, *J. Comput. Chem.* 31 (2) (2010) 455–461, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.21334>.
- [45] S. Vardhan, S.K. Sahoo, Exploring the therapeutic nature of limonoids and triterpenoids against SARS-CoV-2 by targeting nsp13, nsp14, and nsp15 through molecular docking and dynamics simulations, *J. Tradit. Complement Med.* 12 (1) (2022) 44–54, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtcm.2021.12.002>.
- [46] P.A. Velásquez, J.C. Hernandez, E. Galeano, J. Hincapié-García, M.T. Rugeles, W. Zapata-Builes, Effectiveness of drug repurposing and natural products against SARS-CoV-2: a comprehensive review, *Clin. Pharmacol. Adv. Appl.* 16 (2024) 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.2147/Cpaa.S429064>.
- [47] P. V'kovski, A. Kratzel, S. Steiner, H. Stalder, V. Thiel, Coronavirus biology and replication: implications for SARS-CoV-2, *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 19 (3) (2021) 155–170, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-020-00468-6>.
- [48] WHO. (2023). Statement on the Fifteenth Meeting of the International Health Regulations (2005) Emergency Committee Regarding the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Pandemic. Retrieved 18.12.2024 from (<https://www.who.int/news/item/05-05-2023-statement-on-the-fifteenth-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations>)-(2005)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-coronavirus-disease-(covid-19)-pandemic?adgroupsurvey=%7Badgroupsurvey%7D&gclid=EAIaIQobChMI40jtsdbe_gIvJQRyCh07igt4EAAAYASACEgJ9pfd_BwE&fbclid=IwAR2M8EAyisrAodhK9p-X582nHkP2AigpSX8pYIsLspwqYh4SG26RGokGe7E.
- [49] L. Yan, Y. Yang, M. Li, Y. Zhang, L. Zheng, J. Ge, Y.C. Huang, Z. Liu, T. Wang, S. Gao, R. Zhang, Y.Y. Huang, L.W. Guddat, Y. Gao, Z. Rao, Z. Lou, Coupling of N7-methyltransferase and 3'-5' exonuclease with SARS-CoV-2 polymerase reveals mechanisms for capping and proofreading, *e3411*, *Cell* 184 (13) (2021) 3474–3485, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2021.05.033>.
- [50] Y.T. Zhang, H.X. Gao, X.H. Hu, Q.S. Wang, F.L. Zhong, X.L. Zhou, C. Lin, Y. Yang, J. K. Wei, W.A. Du, H.Q. Huang, H. Zhou, W. He, H. Zhang, P.J. McCormick, J.H. Fu, D. Wang, Y. Fu, X.L. Lu, J. Li, Structure-Based discovery and structural basis of a novel Broad-Spectrum natural product against the main protease of coronavirus, *J. Virol.* 96 (1) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01253-21>.